

RETRO-DUODENAL PERFORATES - SURGICAL TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Retro-duodenal perforations / iatrogenic and ulcerative / fortunately, are a relatively rare surgical problem, but unfortunately, in therapeutic aspect, they are associated with severe complications, and still high lethality.

MATERIAL AND METHODS: The subject of study was two groups of patients: in the first, we included patients with gastroduodenal perforations of peptic ulcer. In the second one-the patients were presented with iatrogenic perforations of the duodenum, after endoscopic manipulations on the papilla of Vater. We conduct a retrospective analysis of 5 years period (2011-2015), 6,339 patients underwent surgical operations at the University Hospital "Department of Bilio-Pancreatic Surgery". 15 /0.23%/ cases were included in the first group- patients with retroduodenal perforation of duodenal ulcer.

For the reporting period, a total of 365 patients were indicated to this manipulation: bilio-pancreatitis 78 patients, 74 with mechanical jaundice, 137 with different forms of the biliary-stone disease, 6 with cholangitis and 9 with tumours of extrahepatic bile duct and papilla of Vater. **RESULTS:** In 15 cases we had a retroduodenal perforation of ulcers, three death cases in this group –(20%). In the second group of patients we had 3 cases with Iatrogenic retroduodenal perforation, 2 of them dyed, and lethality was 67% in that group. We performed laparotomy for pyloric occlusion with gastro-jejuno anastomosis and Brown's anastomosis with adequate drainage of retroduodenal space. We inserted two tubes: first for aspiration in the proximal direction in the lumen of the duodenum; the second tube is double lumen nutritional tube. **CONCLUSION:** Retroduodenal perforations, in our opinion, are subject to emergency surgical treatment at the time of their diagnosis. Surgical treatment is obligatory.

KEYWORDS Retro-duodenal perforations, surgery

Introduction

Retro-duodenal perforations / iatrogenic and ulcerative / fortunately, are a relatively rare surgical problem, but unfortunately, in therapeutic aspect, they are associated with severe complications, and still high lethality.

On the other hand, in the last quarter of the century, we have witnessed increasing possibilities of mini-invasive procedures. In addition to diagnostic value, much of them have a therapeutic character, the latter often have either definitive effect. However, we also encounter new iatrogenic complications that are unknown at this moment. Much of these complications are managed conservatively and do not require aggressive surgical interventions. One of the most difficult for diagnosis and treatment complications are retroduodenal perforations. According to the literature, this complication occurs in a frequency of 2-4% of papilla Valery's manipulations. With the intensive work at Gastroenterology diagnostic departments at university and district hospitals, the surgeons need to be familiar and ready to diagnose and treat this kind of complication.

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Surgical treatment in both types of perforations is prevented by the presence of many vital vessels, a nervous network and, on the other hand, retro-duodenal adipose tissue highly susceptible to infection spreading. According to publications in the world literature, some methods of treatment are proposed: conservative, less and more invasive, yet still with variable success and considerably extended hospital staying and expensive cost of treatment.

Material and Methods

The subject of study was two groups of patients: in the first, we included patients with gastroduodenal perforations of peptic ulcer. In the second one-the patients were presented with iatrogenic perforations of the duodenum, after endoscopic manipulations on the papilla of Vater. We conduct a retrospective analysis of 5 years period (2011-2015), 6,339 patients underwent surgical operations at the University Hospital "Department of Bilio-Pancreatic Surgery". 15 /0.23%/ cases were included in the first group- patients with retroduodenal perforation of duodenal ulcer.

In the second group – we collect patients with iatrogenic perforations on the posterior duodenal wall, due to papillosphincterotomy procedure. This is one of the invasive manipulations that is widely used in some diseases of the hepatobiliary tract and pancreatic gland.

In the predominant percentage of patients, papillosphincterotomy procedure can definitively be the solution, while in other cases it is the solution that eliminates the urgent problem and delays the radical intervention at a later stage when patient's general condition become better.

For the reporting period, a total of 365 patients were indicated to this manipulation: bileopancreatitis 78 patients, 74 with mechanical jaundice, 137 with different forms of the biliary-stone disease, 6 with cholangitis and 9 with tumours of extrahepatic bile duct and papilla of Vater. The complications that have been observed are:

1. Haemorrhagic complications – we have 3 /0.8%/ patients with such a complication. This is a relatively low percentage of the frequency, reported in the world literature, but we should point out that our data does not include the cases with manifested bleeding during manipulation. It is managed successfully by endoscopist at the time of manipulation.
2. Increased amylase in blood serum in 5 patients, but in only one it results in edematous pancreatitis!
3. Acute cholangitis. This complication we observed in 4 / 1.4%/ of our patients and after ten days of the period when the patient is already discharged.
4. Iatrogenic perforations of the duodenum. This complication is the rarest- we had it in only three patients /0.8%/, but in all three cases, surgical treatment was strongly recommended. The outcome in two of these patients was, unfortunately, fatal.

The primary accent in the present study is the last complication, as it only led to surgical treatment with high lethality, and according to literature data, the iatrogenic perforations ranged from 4% to 15-20%.(5)

Results

The patients undergoing this study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Patients with retroduodenal perforations.

Patients	Cases	Death	Lethality
Retroduodenal perforation of ulces	15	3	20%
Iatrogenic retroduodenal perforation	3	2	67%
Total	18	5	28%

Discussion

The lethality reported in the literature ranges between 40-75%, especially in the iatrogenic perforations, endoscopic duodenal wall restoration and conservative treatment by aspiration through a nasoduodenal tube.

Our experience shows that these methods are categorically ineffective in perforation of peptic ulcers, and we have a little experience with iatrogenic perforations management.

In general, our tactic is emergency surgery (fig.1) on time of diagnosis.

The operation aims to solve the following tasks:

1. Stop the pathway of gastric juice through the duodenum by ligature on the pylorus area. Through this manipulation, we stop the corrosive action of hydrochloric acid in the area of perforation. We favour the sustained effect of the imposed pyloric ligature. At worst variant, we delay the possible insufficient of the suture, that may happen for a few days after the operation. However, if the latter happens, the lack of gastric juice in the duodenum reduces the amount of fluid flowing back, its aggressive action on the tissues, and favours secondary healing and duodenal fistula formation.
2. Gastro-jejuno anastomosis (most often anterior position to the transverse colon with Brown's anastomosis). It has the task, besides providing the intestinal passage, to make an access to two tubes: first for aspiration in the proximal direction in lumen of duodenum; the second tube is double lumen nutritional tube, which is introduced into the distal intestinal loop and its primary role is to serve for early feeding of the patient . Brown's anastomosis reduces the pressure in the duodenum, especially after removing the aspirational tube and oral feeding the patient starts (Fig.1).
3. Adequate drainage of retroduodenal space with tubular and corrugated drainages. The drainages preserve development of peritonitis, subhepatic abscesses and favour the development of a duodenal fistula. In the postoperative period, we aim to reduce gastric and pancreatic secretion by proton pump inhibitors, H2 blockers, atropine and somatostatin. At the same time, patients receive adequate parenteral therapy, compensating extreme fluids losses. Refeeding of patients usually begins after 10-12 days when we have finished with somatostatin and initially through the food probe while at the same time aspiration of the duodenum continue. Drainages are removed after removal of

Figure 1: Operation in retroduodenal perforations.

the nasogastric tubes. We have taken off those drainages, which are placed at the perforation site at least after the 30th postoperative day, but usually after 60 days.

Three patients had a fistula with a prolonged secretion, and after 70 days it had a high flow rate. One of the patients, the reason for fistula persistence was a high post-operative ileus, which required another surgical intervention. We eliminate the adhesions, after which the fistula closes up to 25 postoperative days. Another fistula management was performed by plom-bage of the external opening of the fistula, and within a week it closed.

Causes of Lethality: One of the cases of death is a rhythm disorder registered on the first postoperative day. In the remaining four patients, the leading cause of the adverse outcome was the uncontrolled inflammation of the duodenum leading to abdominal sepsis, pneumonia and other complications that led to multi-organ failure.

Retroduodenal perforations are still a severe therapeutic problem with high lethality. The reasons are mainly in:

1. A significant number of secretions released into the duode-num as the significant part are highly aggressive to tissues.
2. The presence of vital anatomical structures in this area.
3. The thin, uncovered by parietal peritoneum, posterior wall of the duodenum, which often compromises the sutures in this area.
4. The presence of a significant amount of fat in this area, highly susceptible to infection, which is unlimited in its distribution in this area.

Take home messages:

1. Retroduodenal perforations, in our opinion, are subject to emergency surgical treatment at the time of their diagnosis.

2. Surgical treatment is intended to restore the integrity of the posterior duodenal wall, to break the pathway of hydrochloric acid from the stomach to the duodenum, to provide adequate drainage of the retroduodenal space as well as the possibility of active aspiration into the duodenal lumen.
3. In the postoperative period stringent control of electrolyte balance and all other homeostasis, indicators are necessary.

Competing Interests

No conflict of interest.

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